

UNPACKING THE GLOBALIZATION AND TERRORISM INTERFACE IN SAARC: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE ACROSS ECONOMIC, SOCIAL & POLITICAL DIMENSIONS

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the nexus between globalization and terrorism in South Asian countries from 2003 to 2017 using the PMG autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. This study examines three components of globalization: economic, social, and political globalization. The empirical analysis is conducted in two steps. First, the panel ARDL model is estimated to derive short-run and long-run elasticities. Second, the Granger causality test is conducted to examine the causal relationships among the selected variables. The panel ARDL results indicate a long-run relationship between terrorism and the components of globalization. Political and economic globalization have a positive and statistically significant impact on terrorism, while total globalization also has a positive impact. Additionally, the Granger causality results reveal unidirectional causality running from terrorism to the Political Globalization Index (PGI), unidirectional causality from the Social Globalization Index (SGI) to terrorism, and unidirectional causality from the Total Globalization Index to terrorism.

INTRODUCTION

1. Globalization

The concept of globalization gained popularity in the mid-1990s, both within the social sciences and among the general public. In the business world, globalization is often used to justify firms' activities and provide a basis for international mergers and acquisitions. Globalization contributes to world economies by increasing competition, market connectivity, and foreign direct investment (FDI). However, it also accelerates the absorption of foreign cultures, thoughts, and ideas, which can

negatively impact social and religious norms. The contradictions between foreign ideas, cultures, and the host country's religious and social structures can lead to transnational terrorism.

Globalization has also led to the modification of many values and traditions, facilitated by technologies such as the internet and mobile phones. Cultural changes are reflected in how new lifestyles are perceived. A notable example of this shift in values is the spread of universal ideals, which has had a significant impact on the rise of incentives for global terrorism (Zimmermann,

2011). Scholars offer various definitions of globalization, some linking it to liberalism, others to domination, and some to universalism (Nassar, 2005). This is largely due to the spread of modern Western practices across the world. As a result, traditional customs in many societies are disappearing, replaced by new ones. According to Steger (2013), globalization involves Westernization and Americanization, driving the world toward greater global interconnectedness. As a consequence of globalization, cooperation among various sectors has increased worldwide. However, some experts believe that globalization is a stage in the latest phase of capitalism and modernization, while others view it as a new perspective. Although there are specific definitions in some cases, they cannot entirely eliminate the uncertainty surrounding the term, and interpretations can vary widely (Scholte, 2000). Such shared governance issues can be addressed by investigating the consequences of globalization. In recent decades, the concept of political integration has grown rapidly. In the context of the Memorandum of Understanding and international associations, the benefit of political unity can facilitate a concerted effort to tackle terrorism. Conversely, global political integration can have a negative impact on national politics and domestic sovereignty. In this regard, Roderick (2002) introduced the concept of the political trilemma, arguing that a country's state structure, democratic politics, and economic integration are generally incompatible. Globalization has not always been embraced by all nations; some religious, particularly Islamic, countries have largely rejected globalization. As a result, religious terrorism has increased, leading to a rapid acceleration of globalization (Mekaj & Aliaj, 2018).

By its very nature, globalization has the potential to impact religious values within a society's heritage. The influence of Western cultures has endangered domestic cultures and religions globally. The spread of globalization-related ideas can provoke religious resistance as a response to the perceived threat of cultural homogenization. One consequence of globalization's rise is the

revival of religions around the world (Huntington, 1996)."

SAARC countries are highly economically integrated countries and sustainable development of the region as well as world is highly dependent on the peaceful environment of the countries. SAARC countries are important to the world in many aspects. The region has the world's biggest democratic nation which comprises around 20 percent population of the world. SAARC Countries is highly economically integrated with the rest of the world having trade as percentage of GDP almost 51.30. Recent ongoing projects like China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and India-Iran's Chabahar port projects will enhance inter-regional as well as intra-regional connectivity of the region. However, potential economic benefit from these projects can only be extracted with better law and order conditions in the region. SAARC nations are profoundly economically coordinated nations and adaptable improvement of the area as well as world is exceptionally conditional on the peaceful ailment of the nations. SAARC nations are precarious to the world in numerous viewpoints. The region has the world's greatest domestic country which contains around 20 percent populace of the world. SAARC Countries are profoundly monetarily coordinated with the remainder of the world having exchange as level of GDP practically 51.30. Late progressing tasks like China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and India-Iran's Chabahar port undertakings will improve between local just as intra-local availability of the district. In any case, potential monetary profit by these activities must be removed with better lawfulness conditions in the locale.

The increasing terrorist activity can be the consequences of increasing economic integration/globalization such as the terrorist attack on foreigner from other countries. Increasing linkages among countries can increase the possibilities of informal trade. Besides this, most of the generated from the black market are used in the financing of terrorist activities. One of the main sources of terrorism in the SAARC countries which sharpen the terrorist activity in

the region is the intervention of the US in Afghanistan after the 9/11 attacks.

Despite the strong correlation between terrorism and globalization, the previous literature investigates the primary causes of terrorist activities and their social, political and economic consequences. But very little attention has been paid in case of SAARC countries. It is a terrible need of the time to investigate the relationship between terrorism and globalization in case of SAARC countries, in order to fill the previous literature gap

1.2 Globalization facilitating terrorism

Cronin (2003) argues that the rise of terrorism in recent years, both within states and beyond their borders, is a result of globalization and is facilitated by it. Cronin also suggests that acts of terrorism are not primarily driven by domestic factors, but rather by external influences. The study contends that globalization encompasses various penetrating mechanisms that have been exploited by terrorist networks. Frequently, the web has been distinguished as a helpful apparatus to advance different fear based thoughts. Some product programs permit usability and this brings focal points and thoughts for psychological militant assaults. Since the web is a completely mysterious discussion, it gives clients its utilization for setting up correspondence systems (Goodman, Kirk and Kirk, 2007).

The increased use of the internet by various terrorist organizations has contributed to a rise in the number of planned attacks. Consequently, it is believed that terrorism, especially global terrorism, is facilitated by the internet, which is a product of modern globalization. It is worth mentioning that terrorism has existed for a long time, but access to the internet and technology has only amplified its reach. However, technology has, to some extent, reduced the risk of illegal financial transactions. Then again, this has encouraged understanding among nations and encouraging migration (Zimmermann, 2011). Because of the utilization of innovation and the Internet, the quick exchange of cash to universal fringes has been made conceivable, in this manner diminishing the danger of robbery of cash illicitly

by different psychological oppressor gatherings (Strange, 1998). Zimmermann (2011) likewise contends that the simplicity of transport and move of cash, in addition to other things, has influenced these psychological militant gatherings to practice their activities and to profit by assets. Data advances have empowered psychological oppressor gatherings to arrive at a pinnacle of their vindictive exercises. By utilizing these advances, they can now effectively organize the assaults they plan, however they can likewise misdirect individuals, select them and make them part of their assaults and exercises. In this way, they are as of now utilizing innovation to advance the causes they advocate that have basically viciousness and fear (Heine and Thakur, 2011). The utilization of innovation has given people/bunches access to the outside world. Innovation has influenced correspondence among individuals to develop (Goodman, Kirk and Kirk, 2007) Expanding imbalance over the globe and expanding the hole between poor people and the rich is brought about by globalization. This is accentuated by Nassar (2005). The quantity of individuals with monetary troubles has expanded. Wherever you can see individuals whose economy come and lower. Then again there are individuals who have generally excellent outcomes. The individuals who have financial issues are simpler to turn out to be a piece of fear based oppressor associations. Profoundly created globalization and high financial downturn have prompted expanded viciousness and dissatisfaction. Zimmermann (2011) includes that globalization regularly compounds the level of monetary and social imbalance and polarization inside specific nations. In any event, as indicated by different specialists, the underlying foundations of terrorism can likewise be found in neediness and imbalance. Poor monetary conditions make disappointments, which builds the potential for viciousness. Also, monetary hardship in psychological militant sources is significant in light of the fact that fear-based oppressor associations are effectively selected, new individuals. Low financial conditions can likewise lessen the expenses of savagery. Then again, when we think about riches and destitution all around, financial achievement can draw in psychological warfare (Krieger and

Meierrieks, 2011) All territories that have been considered or treated as unimportant by globalization have been effectively influenced by terrorist oppression. Since these territories are viewed as frail and very helpless against fanatic authoritative opinion, they are simpler to target terrorism oppressor gatherings. In the Middle East, in the Arab nations, which are viewed as politically powerless and monetarily frail, which have not been a piece of globalization, have fallen prey to these gatherings which have endeavored to spread their impact through psychological oppressor savagery. Along these lines, it has been simple for these frail regions to be influenced by terrorist oppressor associations, as referenced prior, individuals in these territories are worn out on monetary wasteful aspects and decide to turn out to be a piece of these perilous gatherings. As indicated by Li and Schaub (2004), a significant factor for the spread of terrorism isn't adequate financial advancement of a nation or neediness. As indicated by the creators, these components make the establishment for expanding the number of terrorist oppressors as individuals join psychological oppressor bunches as a method for demonstrating disappointment and as an approach to take care of their issues. Additionally, Cron includes that poor nations, immature economies, and unpredictability pull in fear monger associations and frequently offer a place

of refuge or can't oust psychological oppressors from their outskirts (Li and Schaub, 2004). Globalization is regularly connected with western culture, empowering one nation's way of life to be actualized in different nations. This can make a few people who don't have similar considerations or conventions with this culture to contradict it (Zimmermann, 2011). Moreover, globalization additionally includes the development of industrialism and market private enterprise, seen as an assault on less advantaged populaces of preservationist societies, since they are hindered by the significant changes realized by the powers of globalization or is discontent with the inconsistent dissemination of advantages (Cronin, 2003). Globalization is regularly viewed as a power that damages the propensities, dialects, and religions of the particular nations. Numerous individuals feel that it wrecks issues in the spots where they live. As motivation to battle against this globalization they think will pulverize their customs and societies, they decide to battle it commandingly and compellingly, along these lines they become some portion of the different fear-based oppressor associations. These individuals decide to battle against the individuals who think about globalization as ordinary and great, individuals who are steady of globalization (Cronin, 2003).

3. Methodology

The conceptual framework of the study is given in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

The universe of this study includes South Asian Countries. For the analysis, data will be taken for the following variables given in table 1 for the period 2003- 2016. The panel data of Globalization, Economic Globalization, Political Globalization, and Social Globalization will be taken from the KOF index. The data of GDP Annual growth will be taken from the World Development Indicator (WDI). The data on terrorism will be collected from the Global Terrorism Database (GTD) sustained by the University of Maryland (Global Terrorism Database 2012). The database contains evidence on the total number of incidents, injuries and death suffered in terrorist attacks. The countries included in this study are Afghanistan, Bhutan, Bangladesh, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka.

The core objective of this study is to investigate the short run and long run relationship between

terrorism and globalization. To achieve the core objective of this study, panel auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) is a suitable econometric model for this study. There are many reasons for the selection of panel ARDL model for this study such as it provides both short run and long run parameter simultaneously. In the short run, if the series deviate from equilibrium this model provides an error correction mechanism which tells us about the time framework in which series diverged to equilibrium in the long run.

This study uses a panel of SAARC countries which include Pakistan, India, Afghanistan, Sri Lanka, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh and Maldives. The sample period is taken from the period of 2003 to 2016. The selection of cross section and time period is purely decided on the base of availability of data. Panel data is generally preferred over time series and cross-sectional data (Hsiao, 2003). Panel data consists of data points, so it provides greater

number of degrees of freedom and reduces the possibility of multicollinearity among explanatory variables. Hence it offers efficient parameter estimate (Hsiao, 2003). Moreover, the effect of unobservable and immeasurable factors could be controlled, each individual heterogeneity could be captured, and the problem of omitted variables could be tackled.

This study uses total globalization as well as factors of globalization such as economic globalization, political globalization, social globalization and terrorism over the period of 2003 to 2016. The dataset on globalization factors is obtained from World Bank database. While observation on terrorism over the required period is obtained from global terrorism index. Final the dataset on real gross domestic product is obtained from World Bank Indicators (WDI).

4. Results

Table 1 Showing results of panel unit root tests. In the current study we had chosen LLC and IPS unit root tests for checking stationary of the purposed variables. The LLC and IPS unit root tests are based on the assumption that variables are independent and identically distributed (*i.i.d.*) across individuals. The LLC unit root test works on the assumption of heterogeneous serial correlation structure of the residuals. However, this test suffers from a major limitation in that it assumes no cross-sectional dependence among the cross-sectional units, while this assumption does not apply in the practical sense. While this limitation of LLC unit root test improved in the (Im Pesaran & Shin, 2003) (IPS) unit root test.

The IPS unit root test accommodates serial correlation and heterogeneity of dynamics. Therefore, considering the limitation of LLC unit root test the study also employed IPS unit root test. The findings presented in table 3 show that TERR, RGDP, PGI, SGI and TGI are stationary at level at the 1% and 5% respectively based on LLC unit root test. While based on IPS TERR, RGDP are only variables which are stationary at level based on IPS. We find conflicting outcomes in level form from both tests hence for the clear decision study checked unit root in first difference and it confirmed that all the variables become stationary after first difference. Generally, findings confirm that TERR and RGDP are those variables which are stationary based on both tests at level I(0). As it also confirms that variables are stationary at mixture some variables are stationary at level and some at first difference, but it is confirmed that non the variable is stationary at second difference.

The unit root outcomes confirmed preconditions of panel ARDL method (PMG), because panel ARDL (PMG) method is equally applicable when the series are purely stationary at level or first difference or mixture of level and first difference. However, there is one limitation of this approach and that is it is not application when there is any variable stationary at second difference present in the model. Hence the finding of unit root tests confirm that variables are at level and first difference (*i.e.* Mixture), therefore, we can proceed for panel ARDL approach which enables us to get short and long-run relationships among the purposed variables.

Table 1: Panel unit Root Test Results

Variables	At Level I(0)		At First difference I(I)	
	LLC	IPS	LLC	IPS
TERR	-4.50 (0.00)*	-2.41 (0.00)**	-7.27 (0.00)*	-5.04 (0.00)*
RGDP	-1.62 (0.05)***	-3.89 (0.08)	-4.67 (0.00)*	-2.27 (0.01)*
EGI	-1.21 (0.11)	-0.72 (0.76)	-7.08 (0.00)*	-4.63 (0.00)*
PGI	-1.63 (0.05)***	0.85 (0.84)	-6.37 (0.00)*	-4.94 (0.00)*

SGI	-2.58 (0.00)*	0.47 (0.68)	-11.43 (0.00)*	-6.31 (0.00)*
TGI	-3.29 (0.00)*	0.13 (0.55)	-8.16 (0.00)*	-4.97 (0.00)*

Note: *,*** refers to level of significance at 1% and 5%

Table 2 shows findings of PMG long-run estimates. The findings confirm that Economics Globalization Index positively and significantly affect terrorism in long run-in south Asia. It implies that 1% increase in EGI leads to increase 37% in terrorism. This relationship implies that economic globalization facilitates the growing information and communication technology potentially throughout the subcontinents which accelerate the integration of people, culture and ideas. Therefore, such movement of materials and ideology facilitate the terrorist action through the subcontinents. This finding of the study is consistent with Davis, (2010), who also postulates there is little doubt that economic globalization positively impacted the expansion and threat of terrorism in Africa. The positive relationship between economic globalization and terrorism is also supported by previous literature such as Asongu & Biekpe (2018); Ahmad & Majeed (2017).

Furthermore, outcomes also confirm a positive association between Political Globalization index and terrorism in long run. It suggests that 1% increase in PGI leads to 14% in terrorism. The relationship suggests that existing political order may be perceived as unfair from the perspective of terrorist group. In such situation terrorist group find it easy to seek support by building on the related grievance in the society. Our finding is matched with previous literature such as Addison and Murshed (2005) who argue that conflict between government and an opposing terrorist group can be exported to foreign ally of the government. Moreover, our study also supports the finding made by Lai, (2007) and Piazza (2008) who's finding also suggest that involvement in the interstate politics ca increase terrorist activities. In the same vein, our study also supports Plumper and Neumayer, (2010) contribution to globalization literature. Plumper and Neumayer ,

(2010) demonstrate that membership of international alliance increase terrorist activities between nation in particular, when there is a major power difference between nation. Asongu & Biekpe (2018) supports the findings of the study, they also explored that political globalization increases terrorism.

On the other hand, it is also observed that Social Globalization index effect terrorism negatively and significantly in the long run. It implies that 1% in SGI reduces terrorism by 35% in long run. This relationship implies that social globalization is mostly concerned with diffusion of developed country culture, thought and ideas in developing countries. The small group in the developing countries did not share the same thought or ideas with other cultures and as a result increased violence in the society. Our result is in line with previous finding of the study made by (Zimmermann, 2011).

Similarly, the outcomes demonstrate that in the long run Total Globalization index negatively and significantly affect terrorism. It implies that in the long run 1% increase in total globalization led to an increase in terrorism by 41% in south Asia. This result implies that the increase in overall integration around the globe increases consumerism and capitalistic market structure. The less privileged population considers capitalism as an attack on their resources. Moreover, the increase in capitalism due to globalization enhances unequal distribution of resources. Therefore, an increase in overall globalization promotes terrorism. Similarly, the findings confirm that Real GDP Growth index also negatively and significantly affect terrorism in Pakistan .it implies that 1% in LR GDP reduce 2.8% in terrorism in long run. This relationship suggests that in time of higher income the opportunity of cost of terrorist activities are high.

Globalization has contributed to the implementation of a country culture in another country that has fueled and spreading terrorism. Globalization has also caused many values and traditions to be changed through new information technologies such as internet, mobile phones, and so on. Changes in tradition also come in the way the new culture is perceived. A particular case of change in value is the emergence and spread of supreme values, which has a major impact on the growth of incentives for international terrorism. Globalization has brought the possibility of facilitating communication with various means between people and countries. At this point, the possibility that terrorist groups may affect different people by making them part of their malicious organizations increased. Transport facilitation has

also made these terrorist groups more likely to increase the number of their members. Globalization has also affected the spread of terrorism, and the techniques used. Moreover, globalization has enabled these terrorist groups to attract members not only domestically but also from other countries. In different countries, globalization is perceived differently. Some countries have reacted badly. At least as far as Islamic groups are concerned, they have clearly responded to the threats that globalization poses to them (Ousman, 2004). Globalization, moreover, involves the movement of goods, services, people, ideas, and cultures across space (Held *et al* 1999: 16).

Table 2: Long run estimates Panel ARDL (PMG estimation)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
EGI	0.371827	0.048930	7.599241	0.0000*
PGI	0.147582	0.023518	6.275298	0.0000*
SGI	-0.357425	0.055274	-6.466450	0.0000*
TGI	0.419007	0.066139	6.335227	0.0000*
LRGDP	-2.820159	0.709466	-3.975047	0.0002*

Table 3 consisting results of short run analysis for the south Asia. The outcomes suggest that all the variables (EGI, PGI, SGI, TGI and EGI) have

insignificant effect on TERR in short run in South Asia. The error correction term show that 25% speed of adjustment.

Table 3: Short-run estimates Panel ARDL (PMG estimation)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
ECT	-0.257087	0.126859	-2.026566	0.0480
D(EGI)	-0.659766	0.559946	-1.178266	0.2442
D(PGI)	-0.779220	0.568150	-1.371504	0.1762
D(SGI)	-0.827117	0.606891	-1.362876	0.1789
D(TGI)	2.164310	1.715298	1.261769	0.2128
D(EGI)	-0.659766	0.559946	-1.178266	0.2442
C	1.574202	0.655427	2.401798	0.0200

Furthermore, present study employed CD test to know either cross-sectional dependence present or not in the model. The outcomes of the CD test are presented in table 4. There are various studies which confirm that normally cross-sectional dependence exists in panel data. Due to the presence of cross-sectional dependence invalid

parameters emerge. The study test CD is based on various statistical tests presented in table 5. The probability value of three employed CD tests accepts null hypothesis, which confirms that model not suffering from cross sectional dependence.

Table 4: Residual Cross-Section Dependence Test

Test	Statistic	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	1.75771	0.2313
Pesaran scaled LM	1.170298	0.2419
Pesaran CD	1.568791	0.1167

Table 5 consisting results of other diagnostic tests (including serial correlation and heteroscedasticity). The study employed Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test for serial correlation and White test for heteroscedasticity. The probability values show that both tests accept

the null hypothesis of no serial correlation and heteroscedasticity. All the findings of the diagnostic tests show that model is not suffering from any said issue, hence the outcomes obtained from panel ARDL (PMG) are reliable and can be used for the policy making.

Table 5: Serial correlation and Heteroskedasticity Test

Diagnostic Test	Description of Test	Probability
Serial correction	The Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test	0.1455
Heteroskedasticity Test:	White test	0.4241

Furthermore, the current study extended analysis using pairwise granger causality test. The outcomes of granger causality tests are presented in table 6. It is observed that uni-directional causality runs

from TERR to PGI. While same uni-directional causality running from SGI to TERR and also uni-directional causality from TGI and TERR.

Table 6: Granger Causality test

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
PGI does not Granger Cause TERR	104	1.68931	0.1967
TERROR does not Granger Cause PGI	104	3.07679	0.0825
SGI does not Granger Cause TERROR	104	0.25394	0.0154
TGI does not Granger Cause TERROR	104	0.00652	0.0358
TERROR does not Granger Cause TGI	104	0.20964	0.6480
LOGRGDP does not Granger Cause TERROR	104	1.44351	0.2324
TERROR does not Granger Cause LOGRGDP	104	0.00568	0.9401

5. Conclusion

This study explores the nexus between globalization and terrorism in eight South Asian countries over the period 2003-2017. Four indicators of globalization—economic, social, political, and total globalization—are employed, with empirical evidence based on the Panel ARDL pooled mean group and Granger causality. The findings confirm that the Economic Globalization Index positively and significantly affects terrorism in the long run in South Asia. Additionally, the results show a positive association between the

Political Globalization Index and terrorism in the long run, suggesting that a 1% increase in PGI leads to a 14% rise in terrorism. Similarly, the findings confirm that the Real GDP Growth Index positively and significantly affects terrorism, implying that a 1% increase in LRGDP leads to a 2.8% rise in terrorism in the long run. On the other hand, the Social Globalization Index is observed to negatively and significantly affect terrorism in the long run, indicating that a 1% increase in SGI reduces terrorism by 35%.

Likewise, the results show that the Total Globalization Index negatively and significantly affects terrorism in the long run, implying that a 1% increase in total globalization leads to a 41% decrease in terrorism in South Asia.

However, the short-run analysis for South Asia reveals that all variables (EGI, PGI, SGI, TGI, and LR GDP) have an insignificant effect on terrorism in the short run. The error correction term indicates a 25% speed of adjustment. All diagnostic test results confirm that the model is free from any issues, ensuring the reliability of the outcomes obtained from the Panel ARDL (PMG) model, which can be used for policymaking." Additionally, the Granger causality results reveal unidirectional causality running from terrorism to the Political Globalization Index (PGI), unidirectional causality from the Social Globalization Index (SGI) to terrorism, and unidirectional causality from the Total Globalization Index to terrorism.

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